

UMUMIY O'RTA TA'LIM MAKTABLARIDA KASRLAR USTIDA TO'RT AMAL MAVZUSINING O'QITILISHI

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Hozirgi bosqichda ta'limning asosiy vazifasi o'quv- tarbiya jarayonini takomillashtirish asosida har tomonlama yetuk, kelajak kishisini tarbiyalash, voyaga etkazishdan iborat. O'quvchilarni barcha kerakli bilim va ko'nikmalar bilan qurollantiruvchi, ularni katta hayotga tayyorlaydigan har bir o'qituvchi hozirgi zamon ijtimoiy- iqtisodiy taraqqiyot masalalarini o'z vaqtida ilg'ab olishi hamda o'zining bor kuch va bilimini, kasb mahoratini takomillashtirishga qaratmog'i, tinmay izlanib mehnat qilmog'i lozim.

O'qituvchi mehnatining samarasi esa u ta'lim berayotgan o'quvchilarning bilim darajasi bilan o'lchanadi. Bilimlar darajasi esa o'quvchilar o'zlashtirishini tekshirish va bilimini baholash jarayonida aniqlanadi. Bu jarayon esa darsdir.

Haqiqatdan ham ta'limning asosiy shakli dars bo'lib, o'quvchilarga asosiy bilim dars davomida beriladi. Shuning uchun eng avvalo ishni o'qituvchi va o'quvchilarning darsga nisbatan yangicha yondashishdan boshlash kerak.

O'quvchilarga chuqur bilim berishda erishgan muvaffaqiyatlarning sirini ham, yo'l qo'yan kamchiliklarimizning sabablarini ham olib borgan darsimizdan izlamoq kerak.

Shunday kasr sonlar borki, ular ustida amallar xuddi natural sonlardagidek oson bajarish mumkin.

Maxraji 10;100;1000 bo'lgan kasrlar yani maxraji bir va undan keyin nollar bo'lgan kasrlar

$\frac{7}{10}, \frac{13}{100}, \frac{17}{1000}, \frac{31}{10000}$

o'nli kasrlar deyiladi. Masalan $\frac{7}{10}$; $\frac{13}{100}$; $\frac{17}{1000}$; $\frac{31}{10000}$.

va ko'plab o'nli kasrga misol keltirishimiz mumkin. O'nli kasrlar maxrajsiz quyidagicha yoziladi: 0,7 0,13 0,017 1,31.

Yani $\frac{7}{10} = 0,7$; $\frac{13}{100} = 0,13$; $\frac{17}{1000} = 0,017$; $\frac{31}{10000} = 1,31$

va bunday o'qiladi : nol butun o'ndan yeti ; nol butun yuzdan o'n uch ; nol butun mingdan o'n yeti ; bir butun yuzdan o'ttiz bir .

Maxraji 10,100,1000,... bo'lgan

$\frac{17}{10}, \frac{3}{10}, 5\frac{7}{10}, \frac{71}{100}, \frac{119}{100}, 2\frac{117}{1000}$

kabi kasrlarni kasr chizig'isiz, ixcham qilib yozish mumkin. Buning uchun, kasrning butun qismini kasr qismidan vergul yordamida ajratish kifoya:

$\frac{17}{10} = 1\frac{7}{10} = 1,7$
(o'qilishi: bir butun o'ndan yetti);

$\frac{71}{100} = 0,71$
(o'qilishi: nol butun yuzdan yetmish bir).

O'nli kasrlarning butun qismi verguldan chap tomonda kasr qismi esa o'ng tomonda yoziladi.

Yuqoridagi kasrlarning maxraji 10 ning darajasidan iborat ekaniga e'tibor bering:

$$10 = 10^1; 100 = 10^2; 1000 = 10^3; \dots$$

Maxraji 10 ning darajasidan iborat bo'lgan kasr o'nli kasr deyiladi.

Demak, $1\frac{7}{10}$ va $1,7$; $\frac{71}{100}$ va $0,71$ kabi yozuvlar ayni bir sonning turli ko'rinishda yozilishidir.

1-qoida. To'g'ri kasrning maxrajidagi 0 lar soni suratidagi raqamlar soniga teng bo'lsa, u holda verguldan o'ng tomonga kasrning surati yoziladi.

Maxraji 10 ning darajasidan iborat oddiy kasrlarni o'nli kasr shaklida yozish qoidasi:

$$\frac{7}{10} = 0,7; \frac{12}{100} = 0,12; \frac{173}{1000} = 0,173$$

2-qoida. To'g'ri kasrning maxragidagi 0 lar soni suratidagi raqamlar sonidan ko'p bo'lsa, u holda suratning chap tomoniga nollar yozish bilan suratdagi raqamlar soni maxrajidagi 0 lar soniga tenglashtiriladi va 1-qoidadan foydalaniladi.

$$\frac{7}{10} = \frac{07}{10} = 0,7; \quad \frac{3}{1000} = \frac{0003}{1000} = 0,003$$

3-qoida. Aralash sonning butun qismidan so'ng vergul qo'yiladi. Kasr qismini yozishda esa 1- yoki 2- qoidadan foydalaniladi.

$$7\frac{8}{10} = 7,8; \quad 3\frac{5}{100} = 3\frac{05}{100} = 3,05; \quad 1\frac{7}{1000} = 1\frac{007}{1000} = 1,007$$

4-qoida. Noto'g'ri kasr aralash son shaklida yozib olinadi va 3-qoida tatbiq qilinadi.

$$\frac{18}{10} = 1\frac{8}{10} = 1,8; \quad \frac{119}{100} = 1\frac{19}{100} = 1,19; \quad \frac{2004}{1000} = 2\frac{4}{1000} = 2\frac{004}{1000} = 2,004$$

Yuqorida ko'rilgan qoida va misollarning o'zi o'nli kasrlarni oddiy kasrga aylantirish yo'llarini ko'rsatadi.

$$1) \quad 0,7 = \frac{7}{10}; \quad 0,12 = \frac{12}{100}; \quad 3) \quad 0,07 = \frac{07}{100} = \frac{7}{100}; \quad 1,007 = 1\frac{7}{1000};$$

$$2) \quad 7,8 = 7\frac{8}{10} = 7\frac{4}{5}; \quad 4) \quad 1,8 = 1\frac{8}{10} = \frac{18}{10} = \frac{9}{5}; \quad 1,19 = 1\frac{19}{100} = \frac{119}{100}.$$

O'nli kasrlarning xona birliklari

O'nli kasrda verguldan keyingi birinchi xona o'ndan birlar xonasi deyiladi. Masalan, 3,7 soni 3 ta bir 7 ta o'ndan birlardan tashkil topgan.

O'nli kasrda verguldan keyingi ikkinchi xona yuzdan birlar xonasi, uchinchi xona esa mingdan birlar xonasi deyiladi va hokazo.

Bu xonalardagi raqamlar, mos ravishda, o'ndan bir ulushlar, yuzdan bir ulushlar, mingdan bir ulushlar sonini bildiradi.

1-misol. 3,745 o'nli kasrda o'ndan birlar xonasida 7, yuzdan birlar xonasida 4, mingdan birlar xonasida 5 raqami turibdi. Bu 3,745 o'nli kasrda 7 ta o'ndan bir ulush, 4 ta yuzdan bir ulush va 5 ta mingdan bir ulush borligini bildiradi, ya'ni

$$3,745 = 3 \frac{745}{1000} = 3 + \frac{700 + 40 + 5}{1000} = 3 + \frac{700}{1000} + \frac{40}{1000} + \frac{5}{1000} = 3 + \frac{7}{10} + \frac{4}{100} + \frac{5}{1000}$$

Zamonaviy maktabning vazifalaridan biri pedagogik jarayonning barcha ishtirokchilarining imkoniyatlarini ochib berish, ularning ijodiy qobiliyatlarini namoyon qilish imkoniyatlarini ta'minlashdir. Ushbu muammolarni hal qilish ta'lim jarayonlarining o'zgaruvchanligini amalga oshirmasdan mumkin emas, bu bilan bog'liq holda chuqur ilmiy va amaliy tushunishni talab qiladigan turli xil innovatsion tip va tipdagi ta'lim muassasalari mavjud.

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